

THEORETICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF FACTORS DETERMINING MENTAL HEALTH

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to mental health and its determinants. An attempt is made to identify the impact of mental health on future generations on a scientific basis.*

Keywords: *Mental health, biological and environmental factors, pathology, concept, physical health, mental and personal qualities.*

Mental health is defined by the World Health Organization as a state of well-being in which an individual can realize his capabilities, withstand certain stresses of life, carry out effective activities, and also contribute to the development of society.

The content of this concept of "mental health" is not limited to medical-psychological criteria, it constantly reflects the norms of a social group that regulate the spiritual life of a person.[1] The World Health Organization reveals the content of the concept of mental health, focusing on the following points:

Mental health is not only the absence of mental disorders.

Mental health is an integral part of health, without mental health there will be no health.

Mental health is determined by a number of socio-economic, biological and environmental factors.

The mental health criteria (signs, characteristics) are based on the concept of "positive mental health" proposed by psychologists in the 1960s. The concept is based on the analysis of the healthy functioning of an individual as a positive process that is characterized meaningfully through the concepts of cognitive self-awareness based on cognitive processes of independent value (K.Goldstein A.Maslow, Sh.Buhler), full-fledged human activity (K. Rogers), authenticity (J. Buzhenthal), striving for meaning (V. Frankl).[2]

Sigmund Freud described mental health as "the ability to love and work". This definition reflects the energy model of the psyche created by Freud, in which healthy development is based on sublimation, that is, the effective redistribution of libido energy to constructive life goals (creativity and intimacy with other people).[2] There are two approaches to determine the state of Health in science: 1) negative definition of Health the absence of pathology of Health; 2) compliance with the written and unwritten spiritual norm adopted in society. The norm here is a synonym for health, and pathology is a synonym for Disease. However, the concepts of norm and pathology are broader than the concepts of Health and disease. The norm and pathology are always constant: they cover the entire complex of transition states. Health and disease act as separate, clearly defined conditions within their limits. They are not associated with objectively recorded deviations from the norm, but with the subjective state of good or bad health, which affects the performance of a person's daily functions in activities, communication and behavior. A distinctive feature of general well-being is the central link in the difference between health and illness. A healthy person is someone who feels good and, therefore, is able to perform daily social functions. A sick person is a person who feels bad and therefore cannot perform daily social functions. At

the same time, the real presence or absence of various deviations from the norm at the biological level of existence is often not decisive for classifying oneself as healthy or sick. For example, people who drink alcohol at a party have deviations from the "normal" parameters of mental activity (they are called "changing states of consciousness"), but they do not get sick until they are sick. They do not interfere with the performance of social functions.

The category of mental and psychological health becomes a central concept that reflects the well-being of people in society. In recent decades, the concept of what health is has changed significantly. The place of the general concept in the quality of somatic activity was taken by a wider range of concepts, including the concepts of mental and psychological health. In the World Health Organization (1946) constitution, health is defined as a state of complete mental, physical and social well-being, not just the absence of illness or disability. The concepts of mental and psychological health are closely related, but not identical. The first component of psychological health is mental health as a result of the comprehensive mental development of a person at all age stages, the implementation of the "desire to be what people can and the gradual realization of their characteristics. Mental and personal qualities. Mental development as the basis of mental health is necessary for a person to acquire culture, gradually accumulate intellectual, volitional and emotional forces in order to fully integrate into the life of the Society of his time. Noted in the "psychological dictionary": the main criteria for mental health are: the compatibility of subjective images with the objects of reflected reality and the nature of reactions – external stimuli, the meaning of life phenomena; the level of age-appropriate maturity of the emotional-volitional and cognitive spheres of the individual; adequacy in micro-social relationships; the ability to self-control behavior, rational planning of life goals and maintaining activity in achieving them, etc. Mental health is very important, but only one of the elements of the phenomenon of a high level of development is psychological health, which ensures a positive relationship of a person with the world. Psychological health is a psychological feature of a developed personality. This is one of the most important cases of personality, associated with the moral development of personality, with the concept of "spiritual development of personality", which occurs on the basis of comprehensive mental development, self-awareness. Features of the development of personality (psychological literacy), the development of spiritual needs, the inclusion of the intangible aspects of being and the formation of the psychological culture of the personality. The basis of the psychological culture of a person is based on the attitude towards a person as the highest value and the understanding of unconditional spiritual responsibility of a person to people, society and himself for his own relationships and behavior as a set of emotional experiences. It allows a person to perceive and understand the feelings and experiences of other people, respond to them, feel empathy, help, conscience, shame, gratitude, etc. [4]

In our study, 163 students from schools 6,10 in the Fergana region and 137 students from schools 10,11 in the Fergana district participated in the empirical study of the self - attitude of adolescents. In order to determine the degree of confidence in oneself, in health, in the realization of future plans, with the knowledge that adolescents are at the core of their anthropometric signs, we are guided by S.R. We conducted a methodology developed by Panteleev called "the study of adolescent self-attitude". The methodology has 9 scales: intimacy, self-confidence, self-control, self-attitude, self-esteem, self-acceptance, self-attachment, inner conflict, self-blame. During the study, we conducted a conversation from adolescents about their dreams in the present time, future goals, feelings of inner feelings that hinder him in the realization of his dreams. We gave them the

necessary Group psychological consultations. After that, readers cosmetics were distributed. Students willingly began to answer questions of methodology. 137 boys and 163 girls participated in this study. The results obtained were processed in Mathematical Statistics and the following results were obtained on the basis of a comparison on the Mann-Whitney U-criterion. The results obtained were given in Table 1.

Table 1

Adolescent self-relation study results n=300

Scales	Gens	Number of testers	Color mean	U (Mann-Whitney value)	p (confidence level)
Closure	Boys	137	139,43	9648,500*	0,040
	Girls	163	159,81		*p≤0,05
Self-confidence	Boys	137	148,51	10893,000	0,712
	Girls	163	152,17		r≥0,05
Self-management	Boys	137	143,95	10268,500	0,227
	Girls	163	156,00		r≥0,05
Specific attitude	Boys	137	146,50	10617,000	0,457
	Girls	163	153,87		r≥0,05
Self-esteem	Boys	137	135,28	9080,000**	0,005
	Girls	163	163,29		**p≤0,01
Self-acceptance	Boys	137	146,51	10618,500	0,461
	Girls	163	153,86		r≥0,05
Self-linking	Boys	137	148,75	10926,000	0,746
	Girls	163	151,97		r≥0,05
Internal conflict	Boys	137	143,79	10246,500	0,217
	Girls	163	156,14		r≥0,05
Self-incrimination	Boys	137	146,34	10596,000	0,443
	Girls	163	153,99		r≥0,05

Note: *p≤0,05; **p≤0,01; ***p≤0,001; r≥0,05

As can be seen from this table, on the proximity scale, a significant difference between the value of it and Mann-Whitney was manifested. in terms of reliability, however, R=0.040; *p<0.05 showed a mid-range difference. According to the analysis of the results obtained, it shows that in boys, overcoming the chosen attitude towards oneself, psychological defenses, manifests such situations as updating others. In girls, however, the personality reflects a clear protective behavior, a desire to adhere to generally accepted standards of behavior and relationships with those around them. In fact, speaking about the concept of “intimacy”, I know two definitions that are given at the same time by famous psychotherapists. The first is E. Erickson’s work defines the concept as “the ability of one person to care for another, to share everything with him without fear of losing himself. E. Bern responded by saying that “intimacy is a man's unplayable, sincere behavior. If any lies do not interfere, it usually does not cause trouble”. As can be seen from the table, in the results of representatives of the two sexes *p≤0.05. That is, the differences in closeness between girls and boys seem to be a bit. This difference showed a higher outcome for boys in girls at 159.81%.

The next scale self-confidence scale is aimed at revealing a relationship in which self-esteem, self-esteem as a confident, independent, strong-willed person, according to the results of a comparison of this scale according to the Mann-Whitney U-criterion $R=0.712$; $r>0.05$ there was no significant level difference between them. The reason for this is manifested in adolescents at this age in the re-formation of a system of interests, goals, ideals in their attitude towards themselves, those around them, in the system of self-awareness, self-assessment, values. In teenage boys, the changes that occur in their body during this period are such that it is at this stage of the child's development that fundamental changes in the course of biological, physiological maturity are realized. Growth of the neck, increased weight, expansion of the chest, changes in the skull, facial part, increased muscle weight and muscle forces, growth of organs and tissues, internal secretion glands, reconstructions in the activity of the nervous system affect the internal state, mood, psyche of adolescents. Sometimes these situations are the basis for the fact that he remains impressive, indifferent, stubborn, aggressive. The next scale is the self-control scale Mann-Whitney U-criterion based on the results of the comparison $R = 0.227$; $r>0.05$ between them, the difference in the degree of importance of ham was not determined. The reason for this reflects in adolescents his idea of the main source of his activity, results and achievements, the source of personal development, emphasizing the superiority of his "I" or external circumstances. At this age, the influence of microenvironment (Family, School) members is important in adolescent self-awareness. If a parent is aware of the psychology of pedagogical age periods, and in the educational process, using this knowledge in relationships, the importance of "I" in adolescents increases, he learns to analyze himself. The fact that adolescents realize their capabilities and abilities and strive to find their place everywhere provides a thorough basis for the improvement of self-awareness. Adolescents choose the ideal image for themselves, trying and striving to resemble it. During this period, parents and loved ones should help him choose the right ideal. That is, in order not to be mistaken for non-verbal fantasies, wrong choice (beautiful, wealthy, ultra-modern, light-hearted), it was found that parents, educators need to explain in adolescents the importance of social sets, position formation, the concept of happiness, human qualities, strong will and positive character qualities. According to the results of the comparison on the Mann - Whitney U-criterion on the next self-reflection scale $R=0.457$; $R>0.05$ on this scale, no significant level difference was detected between the hams. This scale describes the idea of a teenager in terms of his ability to arouse respect and empathy in other people. This is due to the fact that the main psychological factors in the formation of self-awareness in adolescents are family, school, social environment and social activity. In adolescence, when a child needs to be able to exchange ideas with family members about the psychological and physiological changes that are taking place in him, a healthy psychological environment is created in the family, the relationship between parents and children is friendly, based on understanding, adolescents feel free at this age. Discussing with adolescents his studies, material condition, comrades, interests, encouraging his achievements, correctly showing his shortcomings are the reason for the formation in him of self-discipline, internal discipline, responsibility. On the next self-esteem scale of the study, the Mann-Whitney U-criterion showed Ham based on a comparison of 9080,000**. Differences in results according to the degree of reliability $R=0.005$; $**p<0.01$ result occurred and a significant degree difference was observed between them. The reason for this self-esteem is the complete acceptance of oneself in adolescents at this young age. It is the appearance in adolescents of inner harmony, integrity, a sense of self-confidence. This concept is often confused with self-esteem, but the

difference is huge. Unlike self-esteem, self-esteem does not change from a random word or comment, it has been found that it does not depend on the field of activity, appearance, weight or health. On this scale, self-esteem was found to be higher in female adolescents compared to male Bol. According to this, in girls, however, cases of wealth of their inner world, perception of oneself as a person, self-confidence, rational acceptance of criticism were highly manifested. A teenage girl is the future mother, the follower of the nation, the representative of the Holy One. It is necessary to understand its health, behavior, susceptibility to external influences, protection from negative influences, self-esteem and the impact of the social environment on teenage girls. In this regard, the president of Uzbekistan SH.M. Mirziyoev said: "... a girl is the future mistress of the family, the owner of our future. How we educate them today, how they educate our new generation tomorrow." The next scale was the self-acceptance scale, and no significant level difference was found between the criteria of adolescents. $r=0.461$; $R > 0.05$. This is due to the fact that at this age, teenage boys fully recover from the previous internal conflicts in it, the formation and consequent new qualitative state of their connection, which is intended to be realized by their subectedness in the process of self – realization and acceptance. Therefore, adolescents in this scientific approach, the function of self–awareness as a continuous mental process is determined by the conflict between a person's perception of other people and their attitudes towards it. Even on the next scale self-linking scale, no significant differences were found in the results of teenage boy girls ($r=0.746$; $R>0.05$). According to the results obtained on this scale, it was shown that the chosen attitude to one's own personal characteristics, the desire to change only some of his qualities while retaining others, is clearly manifested in adolescents. Significant differences in the next i.e. internal conflict of the study as well as self-incrimination scales were not identified- $r=0.217$; $R>0.05$, $R=0.443$; $R>0.05$. According to him, adolescents showed signs of internal contradictions, doubts, the presence of self-dissension, the seriousness of introspection and meditative tendencies. In conclusion, it should be said that within the framework of this methodology, the teenage boy showed only significant level differences between girls on the scales of intimacy and self-esteem. Whereas, therefore, the realization by a person at the essence and level of his sociability, that is, humanity, is the process of creating from a psychological point of view the understanding of the essence of these needs, interests, aspirations, as well as his personal purpose for life, activities. From the above considerations, adolescent self-awareness is based on moral spiritual norms and rules, affirmation as human beings and thus their aspirations towards the formation of humanity in oneself.

REFERENCES

1. Family Studies psychodiagnostic methodologies. Developers: N.A.Soginov, F.G'.Habibullaev. - T.,: 1996. -38 b.
2. ShoumarovSh.B., Shoumarov G'.B.Love and family life. - T.,- Ibn Sina, 1996. -96 b.
3. Kovalev S.V. Psixologiya sovremennoy semi. –M., 1988
4. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted on December 8, 1992 at the eleventh session of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan of the twelfth convocation. - T.: Uzbekistan, 1992-48 b.
5. Mirziyoev SH.M. "We will build a free and prosperous democratic state of Uzbekistan together."- T.: "Uzbekistan" -2016.

6. Mirziyoev SH.M. "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people." - T.: "Uzbekistan" -2017.
7. Musurmonova, Abdurakhimova" healthy lifestyle of girls in the neighborhood " T. 2008.
8. Avloni Abdullah. Turkish Gulistan or morality. - T.: Teacher, 1992. – 160 b.
9. Azizhoujaeva N.N. Technology of preparation for the teacher's specialty. - T.: TDPU, 2000. – 52 b.
10. Akramova F.A. Main problems of providing psychological service to the family // Ilim ha'm ja'miyet, Нукус, 2020 № 4. -P.105-107 (19.00.00. № 2).
11. Akramova F.A. The divorce factors of families and psychological service to the family. //International Scientific Journal ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science Philadelphia, USA issue 01, volume 81, 325-328. published January 30, 2020. (19.00.00. № 3).
12. Akramova F.A. Socio-psychological problems early marriage in Uzbekistan // Theoretical & Applied Science International Scientific Journal, Year: 2020 Issue: 06 Volume: 86 Published: 30.06.2020 p. 405-415. (19.00.00.№ 3).
13. Akramova F.A. Main requirements psychological service for families// European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Science, Great Britain Progressive Academic Publishing. [Electronic resource]. 2020, October, 8 (10), Part II, 16-18.(19.00.00.№2).
14. Akramova F.A. Psychological service and models of psychological assistance family as a necessary factor of family strengthening // ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, India. Vol 11, Issue 4, April 2021, ImpactFactor: SJIF 2021=7,492 P.1574-1579. (19.00.00. № 2).
15. Акрамова Ф.А. Психологические особенности готовности старшеклассников к семейным отношениям. Семья и дети в современном мире. Сборник материалов конференции. Том VI. -СПб.: Изд. РГПУ им. А.И.Герцена, 2020. -1468 с. С. 37-41.
16. Акрамова Ф.А. Предназначение и социально-психологические проблемы семей в Узбекистане // «Научные исследования XXI века» 2020 № 5. - С. 319-323.Дата выпуска– 28.06.2020 г. ISSN: 2713-14084.
17. Солиев, Ф. С., Абдуллаева, А. Р., & Джухонова, Н. Х. (2019). Формирование психологической культуры и этноценностных ориентаций студенческой молодежи. *Психологическое благополучие современного человека* (pp. 334-339).
18. Djuxonova N.X., Mamajonova SH. Mahalla-qizlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlashning muhim omili sifatida //innovatsii v pedagogike i psixologii. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 7.
19. Исакова, М. Т. "Эмпирическое исследование взаимосвязи отношения личности к здоровью с индивидуально-динамическими характеристиками" П 86 Психология управления персоналом и экосистема наставничества в условиях изменения технологического уклада. Вторая международная научно (2021): 544.
20. Isaqova M. T. Etnopsixologiya //Toshkent: Iqbol-Turon. – 2007.
21. Ostanakulov A.D The history and role of Islam and psychology in the education system in Central Asia. ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions <https://RESERCHJET.ACADEMIASCIENCE.ORG> ISSN: 2776-0960 Impact Factor: 7.655 V O L U M E 2, I S S U E 4, A P R I L - 2 0 2 1
22. Abduqodirova L. Y., Sobirova A. Iqtidorli o'quvchilarda samarali koping xulq-atvorni shakllantirish mamlakat inson kapitalini rivojlantirish omili sifatida //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 1357-1363.

23. Rustamovna, Abdullaeva Arofat, and Djukhonova Noxida. Ethnopsychological features of the preparation of student girls for family life. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 11(5) (2021): 974-979.
24. Джухонова Н. Подготовка учащихся к семейной жизни как психолого-педагогическая проблема //ББК Ю953. – 2020. – С. 68.
25. Djuhonova N. Preparing students for family life as a pedagogical and psychological problem //Психологическое здоровье населения как важный фактор обеспечения процветания общества. – 2020. – С. 68-71.
26. Джухонова, Нохида Хаётжоновна, and Дониёр Иброхимов. ЭТНОПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОДГОТОВКИ ДЕВУШЕК-СТУДЕНТОК К СЕМЕЙНОЙ ЖИЗНИ //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 829-835.